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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASEEB.A.S** bearing USN **3SU19SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASHIM ANSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM SHANKAR M** bearing USN **3SU19SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU19SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK BOBY** bearing USN **3SU19SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH KAKKARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHEENA RANJITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFDHAL ABDELQADIR** bearing USN **3SU19SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEMA IZMATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUPAM P** bearing USN **3SU19SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG** bearing USN **3SU19SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FLOSSY J FERNANDES** bearing USN **3SU19SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G JEEVITHA** bearing USN **3SU19SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLERAN WILSON DIAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWDA ARCHANA DEVARAJ MANJULA** bearing USN **3SU19SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** bearing USN **3SU19SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITHIK** bearing USN **3SU19SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KHAZIN** bearing USN **3SU19SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAJOL BEKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHI.P** bearing USN **3SU19SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA B** bearing USN **3SU19SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FIRAZ** bearing USN **3SU19SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIZWAN B** bearing USN **3SU19SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASBHAR SHAH** bearing USN **3SU19SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASFAK** bearing USN **3SU19SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHFAQ C H** bearing USN **3SU19SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AWAIS RASHEED** bearing USN **3SU19SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED INSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAZAR K S** bearing USN **3SU19SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEER C A** bearing USN **3SU19SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAHER** bearing USN **3SU19SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN MUZHAMIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU19SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED SABITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MULTAZAM SHEIKH** bearing USN **3SU19SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA K** bearing USN **3SU19SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWFA ZAHINAB** bearing USN **3SU19SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEERAJA M S** bearing USN **3SU19SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU19SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHAN BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU19SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN K R** bearing USN **3SU19SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NUMAN MAHAMMED SAYED** bearing USN **3SU19SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV T V** bearing USN **3SU19SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIKSHA POOVAPPA SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU19SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRUTHVI** bearing USN **3SU19SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL S** bearing USN **3SU19SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMSEENA** bearing USN **3SU19SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIMEMKI DKHAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFAN P K** bearing USN **3SU19SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHADIN MALIYAKKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARIFA DHANIYA** bearing USN **3SU19SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAM H** bearing USN **3SU19SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDDHARTH K M** bearing USN **3SU19SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA M** bearing USN **3SU19SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V JEEVAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASAR K A** bearing USN **3SU19SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASHWITH B** bearing USN **3SU19SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YUSRA KATIB** bearing USN **3SU19SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUNEEES A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SINAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RADIL AFRAS A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFTHAB SHEIK** bearing USN **3SU19CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED NIBRAS ABDULLA M** bearing USN **3SU19CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA** bearing USN **3SU19CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAMPASHREE BOLLUR** bearing USN **3SU19CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPTHI** bearing USN **3SU19CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEETANJALI MAHALE** bearing USN **3SU19CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH KULAL** bearing USN **3SU19CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSWIN DSILVA** bearing USN **3SU19CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN S** bearing USN **3SU19CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMSHUDEEN** bearing USN **3SU19CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFIL FARHAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMAD ABDUL HADI** bearing USN **3SU19CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRITHVIRAJ P** bearing USN **3SU19CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROOPESH** bearing USN **3SU19CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH S KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK** bearing USN **3SU19CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUNIL K** bearing USN **3SU19CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAJ A** bearing USN **3SU19CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHMA** bearing USN **3SU19CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASEEB.A.S** bearing USN **3SU19SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASHIM ANSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM SHANKAR M** bearing USN **3SU19SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU19SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK BOBY** bearing USN **3SU19SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH KAKKARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHEENA RANJITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFDHAL ABDELQADIR** bearing USN **3SU19SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEMA IZMATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUPAM P** bearing USN **3SU19SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG** bearing USN **3SU19SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FLOSSY J FERNANDES** bearing USN **3SU19SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G JEEVITHA** bearing USN **3SU19SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLERAN WILSON DIAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWDA ARCHANA DEVARAJ MANJULA** bearing USN **3SU19SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** bearing USN **3SU19SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITHIK** bearing USN **3SU19SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KHAZIN** bearing USN **3SU19SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAJOL BEKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHI.P** bearing USN **3SU19SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA B** bearing USN **3SU19SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FIRAZ** bearing USN **3SU19SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIZWAN B** bearing USN **3SU19SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASBHAR SHAH** bearing USN **3SU19SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASFAK** bearing USN **3SU19SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHFAQ C H** bearing USN **3SU19SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AWAIS RASHEED** bearing USN **3SU19SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED INSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAZAR K S** bearing USN **3SU19SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEER C A** bearing USN **3SU19SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAHER** bearing USN **3SU19SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN MUZHAMIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU19SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED SABITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MULTAZAM SHEIKH** bearing USN **3SU19SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA K** bearing USN **3SU19SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWFA ZAHINAB** bearing USN **3SU19SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEERAJA M S** bearing USN **3SU19SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU19SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHAN BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU19SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN K R** bearing USN **3SU19SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NUMAN MAHAMMED SAYED** bearing USN **3SU19SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV T V** bearing USN **3SU19SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIKSHA POOVAPPA SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU19SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRUTHVI** bearing USN **3SU19SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL S** bearing USN **3SU19SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMSEENA** bearing USN **3SU19SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIMEMKI DKHAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFAN P K** bearing USN **3SU19SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHADIN MALIYAKKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARIFA DHANIYA** bearing USN **3SU19SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAM H** bearing USN **3SU19SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDDHARTH K M** bearing USN **3SU19SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA M** bearing USN **3SU19SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V JEEVAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASAR K A** bearing USN **3SU19SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASHWITH B** bearing USN **3SU19SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YUSRA KATIB** bearing USN **3SU19SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUNEEES A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SINAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RADIL AFRAS A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFTHAB SHEIK** bearing USN **3SU19CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED NIBRAS ABDULLA M** bearing USN **3SU19CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA** bearing USN **3SU19CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAMPASHREE BOLLUR** bearing USN **3SU19CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPTHI** bearing USN **3SU19CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEETANJALI MAHALE** bearing USN **3SU19CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH KULAL** bearing USN **3SU19CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSWIN DSILVA** bearing USN **3SU19CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN S** bearing USN **3SU19CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMSHUDEEN** bearing USN **3SU19CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFIL FARHAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMAD ABDUL HADI** bearing USN **3SU19CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRITHVIRAJ P** bearing USN **3SU19CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROOPESH** bearing USN **3SU19CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH S KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK** bearing USN **3SU19CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUNIL K** bearing USN **3SU19CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAJ A** bearing USN **3SU19CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHMA** bearing USN **3SU19CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASEEB.A.S** bearing USN **3SU19SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASHIM ANSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM SHANKAR M** bearing USN **3SU19SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU19SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK BOBY** bearing USN **3SU19SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH KAKKARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHEENA RANJITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFDHAL ABDELQADIR** bearing USN **3SU19SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEMA IZMATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUPAM P** bearing USN **3SU19SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG** bearing USN **3SU19SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FLOSSY J FERNANDES** bearing USN **3SU19SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G JEEVITHA** bearing USN **3SU19SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLERAN WILSON DIAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWDA ARCHANA DEVARAJ MANJULA** bearing USN **3SU19SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** bearing USN **3SU19SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITHIK** bearing USN **3SU19SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KHAZIN** bearing USN **3SU19SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAJOL BEKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHI.P** bearing USN **3SU19SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA B** bearing USN **3SU19SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FIRAZ** bearing USN **3SU19SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIZWAN B** bearing USN **3SU19SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASBHAR SHAH** bearing USN **3SU19SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASFAK** bearing USN **3SU19SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHFAQ C H** bearing USN **3SU19SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AWAIS RASHEED** bearing USN **3SU19SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED INSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAZAR K S** bearing USN **3SU19SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEER C A** bearing USN **3SU19SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAHER** bearing USN **3SU19SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN MUZHAMIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU19SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED SABITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MULTAZAM SHEIKH** bearing USN **3SU19SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA K** bearing USN **3SU19SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWFA ZAHINAB** bearing USN **3SU19SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEERAJA M S** bearing USN **3SU19SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU19SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHAN BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU19SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN K R** bearing USN **3SU19SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NUMAN MAHAMMED SAYED** bearing USN **3SU19SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV T V** bearing USN **3SU19SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIKSHA POOVAPPA SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU19SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRUTHVI** bearing USN **3SU19SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL S** bearing USN **3SU19SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMSEENA** bearing USN **3SU19SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIMEMKI DKHAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFAN P K** bearing USN **3SU19SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHADIN MALIYAKKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARIFA DHANIYA** bearing USN **3SU19SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAM H** bearing USN **3SU19SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDDHARTH K M** bearing USN **3SU19SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA M** bearing USN **3SU19SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V JEEVAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASAR K A** bearing USN **3SU19SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASHWITH B** bearing USN **3SU19SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YUSRA KATIB** bearing USN **3SU19SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUNEEES A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SINAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RADIL AFRAS A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFTHAB SHEIK** bearing USN **3SU19CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED NIBRAS ABDULLA M** bearing USN **3SU19CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA** bearing USN **3SU19CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAMPASHREE BOLLUR** bearing USN **3SU19CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPTHI** bearing USN **3SU19CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEETANJALI MAHALE** bearing USN **3SU19CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH KULAL** bearing USN **3SU19CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSWIN DSILVA** bearing USN **3SU19CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN S** bearing USN **3SU19CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMSHUDEEN** bearing USN **3SU19CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFIL FARHAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMAD ABDUL HADI** bearing USN **3SU19CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRITHVIRAJ P** bearing USN **3SU19CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROOPESH** bearing USN **3SU19CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH S KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK** bearing USN **3SU19CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUNIL K** bearing USN **3SU19CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAJ A** bearing USN **3SU19CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHMA** bearing USN **3SU19CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASEEB.A.S** bearing USN **3SU19SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASHIM ANSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM SHANKAR M** bearing USN **3SU19SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU19SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK BOBY** bearing USN **3SU19SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH KAKKARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHEENA RANJITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFDHAL ABDELQADIR** bearing USN **3SU19SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEMA IZMATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUPAM P** bearing USN **3SU19SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG** bearing USN **3SU19SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FLOSSY J FERNANDES** bearing USN **3SU19SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G JEEVITHA** bearing USN **3SU19SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLERAN WILSON DIAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWDA ARCHANA DEVARAJ MANJULA** bearing USN **3SU19SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** bearing USN **3SU19SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITHIK** bearing USN **3SU19SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KHAZIN** bearing USN **3SU19SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAJOL BEKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHI.P** bearing USN **3SU19SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA B** bearing USN **3SU19SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FIRAZ** bearing USN **3SU19SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIZWAN B** bearing USN **3SU19SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASBHAR SHAH** bearing USN **3SU19SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASFAK** bearing USN **3SU19SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHFAQ C H** bearing USN **3SU19SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AWAIS RASHEED** bearing USN **3SU19SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED INSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAZAR K S** bearing USN **3SU19SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEER C A** bearing USN **3SU19SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAHER** bearing USN **3SU19SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN MUZHAMIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU19SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED SABITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MULTAZAM SHEIKH** bearing USN **3SU19SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA K** bearing USN **3SU19SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWFA ZAHINAB** bearing USN **3SU19SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEERAJA M S** bearing USN **3SU19SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU19SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHAN BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU19SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN K R** bearing USN **3SU19SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NUMAN MAHAMMED SAYED** bearing USN **3SU19SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV T V** bearing USN **3SU19SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIKSHA POOVAPPA SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU19SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRUTHVI** bearing USN **3SU19SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL S** bearing USN **3SU19SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMSEENA** bearing USN **3SU19SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIMEMKI DKHAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFAN P K** bearing USN **3SU19SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHADIN MALIYAKKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARIFA DHANIYA** bearing USN **3SU19SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAM H** bearing USN **3SU19SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDDHARTH K M** bearing USN **3SU19SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA M** bearing USN **3SU19SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V JEEVAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASAR K A** bearing USN **3SU19SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASHWITH B** bearing USN **3SU19SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YUSRA KATIB** bearing USN **3SU19SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUNEEES A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SINAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RADIL AFRAS A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFTHAB SHEIK** bearing USN **3SU19CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED NIBRAS ABDULLA M** bearing USN **3SU19CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA** bearing USN **3SU19CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAMPASHREE BOLLUR** bearing USN **3SU19CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPTHI** bearing USN **3SU19CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEETANJALI MAHALE** bearing USN **3SU19CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH KULAL** bearing USN **3SU19CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSWIN DSILVA** bearing USN **3SU19CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN S** bearing USN **3SU19CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMSHUDEEN** bearing USN **3SU19CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFIL FARHAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMAD ABDUL HADI** bearing USN **3SU19CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRITHVIRAJ P** bearing USN **3SU19CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROOPESH** bearing USN **3SU19CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH S KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK** bearing USN **3SU19CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUNIL K** bearing USN **3SU19CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAJ A** bearing USN **3SU19CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHMA** bearing USN **3SU19CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASEEB.A.S** bearing USN **3SU19SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HASHIM ANSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIRAM SHANKAR M** bearing USN **3SU19SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU19SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK BOBY** bearing USN **3SU19SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH KAKKARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADHEENA RANJITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFDHAL ABDELQADIR** bearing USN **3SU19SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEEMA IZMATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUPAM P** bearing USN **3SU19SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIRAG** bearing USN **3SU19SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FLOSSY J FERNANDES** bearing USN **3SU19SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G JEEVITHA** bearing USN **3SU19SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GLERAN WILSON DIAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWDA ARCHANA DEVARAJ MANJULA** bearing USN **3SU19SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRIDHYA K P** bearing USN **3SU19SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITHIK** bearing USN **3SU19SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM KHAZIN** bearing USN **3SU19SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAJOL BEKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHI.P** bearing USN **3SU19SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA B** bearing USN **3SU19SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FIRAZ** bearing USN **3SU19SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIZWAN B** bearing USN **3SU19SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU19SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASBHAR SHAH** bearing USN **3SU19SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASFAK** bearing USN **3SU19SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASHFAQ C H** bearing USN **3SU19SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AWAIS RASHEED** bearing USN **3SU19SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED INSHAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED JAZAR K S** bearing USN **3SU19SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SAHEER C A** bearing USN **3SU19SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAHER** bearing USN **3SU19SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOIDEEN MUZHAMIL** bearing USN **3SU19SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU19SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED SABITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MULTAZAM SHEIKH** bearing USN **3SU19SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA K** bearing USN **3SU19SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAWFA ZAHINAB** bearing USN **3SU19SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NEERAJA M S** bearing USN **3SU19SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU19SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHAN BANGERA** bearing USN **3SU19SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN K R** bearing USN **3SU19SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NUMAN MAHAMMED SAYED** bearing USN **3SU19SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAV T V** bearing USN **3SU19SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU19SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIKSHA POOVAPPA SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU19SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRUTHVI** bearing USN **3SU19SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAHUL S** bearing USN **3SU19SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJATH** bearing USN **3SU19SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMSEENA** bearing USN **3SU19SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIMEMKI DKHAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFAN P K** bearing USN **3SU19SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHADIN MALIYAKKAL** bearing USN **3SU19SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARIFA DHANIYA** bearing USN **3SU19SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAM H** bearing USN **3SU19SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDDHARTH K M** bearing USN **3SU19SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THEERTHA M** bearing USN **3SU19SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V JEEVAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU19SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASAR K A** bearing USN **3SU19SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YASHWITH B** bearing USN **3SU19SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YUSRA KATIB** bearing USN **3SU19SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUNEEES A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SINAN** bearing USN **3SU19SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RADIL AFRAS A M** bearing USN **3SU19SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFTHAB SHEIK** bearing USN **3SU19CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED NIBRAS ABDULLA M** bearing USN **3SU19CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA** bearing USN **3SU19CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAMPASHREE BOLLUR** bearing USN **3SU19CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEPTHI** bearing USN **3SU19CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEETANJALI MAHALE** bearing USN **3SU19CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH KULAL** bearing USN **3SU19CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSWIN DSILVA** bearing USN **3SU19CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN S** bearing USN **3SU19CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMSHUDEEN** bearing USN **3SU19CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFIL FARHAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMAD ABDUL HADI** bearing USN **3SU19CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRITHVIRAJ P** bearing USN **3SU19CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH** bearing USN **3SU19CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROOPESH** bearing USN **3SU19CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH S KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU19CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHASHANK** bearing USN **3SU19CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUNIL K** bearing USN **3SU19CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAJ A** bearing USN **3SU19CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHMA** bearing USN **3SU19CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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